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Demographic Factors In Marital Satisfaction Among Female Public Secondary School Teachers In Rivers West Senatorial District Of Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated demographic factors in marital satisfaction among female public secondary school teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State. Descriptive research design was employed in the study. The population of study comprised 32,504 married teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State. Multi-stage and stratified sampling technique was utilized in selecting the sample size of 400 for the study. The instrument for data collection was a researcher designed questionnaire titled: “Marital Satisfaction Assessment Scale (MSAS)”. The instrument was validated by two experts. The data collected was analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and independent sample t-test to test the null hypotheses 1, 2,4, while ANOVA was used to test null hypothesis 3 all at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean response of female teachers on factors in marital satisfaction among female secondary school teachers based on years in marriage, level of education, age in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State. It was recommended amongst other that married teachers in the district should endeavour to balance work and marriage on other to enjoy marital satisfaction.

Keywords: Demographic factors, marital satisfaction, female secondary school teachers

INTRODUCTION

In contemporary times people who are unmarried are regarded as irresponsible, this may be as a result of the stability and sense belonging that married people enjoy. The charms and peace that marriage brings to humans often reflect in all endeavours and dispositions, irrespective of a person's job, colour, ethnic, religious, social affluence or race marriage is noted and seen as not just sacred but pertinent. There are many goals of marriage, these goals vary from couple to couple. The researchers believes that the most important goal of marriage is the attainment of marital satisfaction. As marital satisfaction gives rise to productivity and credibility (Heshmati et al., (2016). Rebello et al. (2014) views marital satisfaction as a complex and multi-dimensional phenomenon, which has been extensively explored by researchers in the most diverse scientific fields. Marital satisfaction is a thorough evaluation of the state of one's marriage to ascertain the reflection of marital happiness, personal happiness and functioning. In contemporary times marital satisfaction can be viewed as a psychological state of regulated mechanisms that monitor the benefits and detriments of marriage in the live of an individual (Obiekwe & Ekebosi, 2021).

Farahmand and Ahmadnia (2014) buttressed that in the definition of marital satisfaction should include the subjective assessment of the quality of relationship shared among married persons. It is thus

imperative to note that the factors which influence or contribute to marital satisfaction may differ across jobs, cultures, income level, ethnic and religion. Adzido et al. (2016) asserted that marriage is more of an economic relation and a secure social network than an emotional relationship. Income, job, properties, debt, and division of chores at home form the quality and stability of married life. In other words, income, expenditure, saving, and sharing money are inseparable components of married life in the current era. In Nigeria for example, the job and income of the husband who is regarded as the head of the family may be an important factor in the analysis of marital satisfaction, this may not be so in other countries in the United States and Europe.

Effective factors in marital satisfaction were categorized in demographic, interpersonal, psychological, interaction, spiritual-religious, and sexual factors. Taghani et al. (2019) asserted that marital satisfaction, as one of the indicators of the quality of marriage, is a genuine feeling of pleasure, satisfaction, and joyfulness experienced by a husband and wife when they consider all aspects of their marriage. The state of adaptation between the expected situation and the current situation of an individual, in marital relations, would develop marital satisfaction which is the most important factor for the durability of married life among teachers (Sosan, 2014). Aidoo et al., (2024) opined that marital satisfaction actually indicates the interest and sympathy of couples toward each other and their positive attitude to being married. After marriage, individuals seek a life full of happiness and satisfaction; therefore, more significant than the marriage itself is success in marriage and marital satisfaction (Narimani et al., 2015).

Marital satisfaction can lead to fulfillment of many physical and psychological needs, and in case of failure, couples and especially children will be faced with severe psychological trauma (Taghizadel et al., 2015). It is obvious that numerous factors play a role in marital satisfaction. The couples' personality, the level of mutual understanding, intellectual maturity, sufficient mental balance, economic factors, computability, sexual satisfaction, love, and passion are among the most important factors in creating a satisfactory life (Kamaley et al. (2014). Farzanel et al. (2016) indicated that some items related to demographic factors of married couples like (age difference with the spouse, marriage duration, education, the number of children, economic situation, and income) are significant factors of marital satisfaction. Marzie et al., (2015) in their study unraveled that financial issues are the commonest sources of conflicts in interpersonal, marital, and family relationships and appropriate employment and income are important issues in establishing, maintaining, and increasing marital satisfaction. It is observed that financial problems and low income can cause conflict, lower marital satisfaction and divorce between couples (Ukaegbu & Ekott 2025) decrease in marital satisfaction does not only create an inappropriate atmosphere in a family but also leads to unproductivity, family instability and divorce.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Marital satisfaction is a multifaceted construct that is influenced by a myriad of factors, and its dynamics become even more intricate within specific occupational groups. Teachers, as a professional cohort, often contend with unique stressor and demands that can impact their overall well-being and, consequently, their marital satisfaction. Understanding the factors that contribute to marital satisfaction among teachers is not only pertinent for the individuals involved but also holds implications for the broader educational community. Research indicates that occupational stress and its spill-over effects on personal life are particularly pronounced in the teaching profession (Caponecchia & Wyatt, 2011).

The nature of teaching is that of a dynamic, professional, and relational process focused on facilitating learning, while the nature of marriage is a sacred, permanent, and sacrificial covenant designed for partnership and companionship. Both roles demand high levels of commitment, preparation, and skill to navigate their respective challenges, often requiring individuals to manage both as competing, yet deeply personal, and responsibilities. As teachers grapple with high workloads, student-related challenges, and institutional pressures, their ability to maintain a satisfying marital relationship becomes a significant consideration. Moreover, the nature of teaching, with its emotional labour and intense interpersonal interactions, can have repercussions on the emotional well-being of educators and, consequently, on the dynamics of their marriages. Sadeghi et al., (2018)

High workload and stress levels associated with teaching can impact marital satisfaction (Smith & Allen, 2019). Effective stress management strategies and open communication between spouses are essential for mitigating the negative effects. Achieving a balance between professional responsibilities and personal life is vital for marital satisfaction (Clark, 2018). Supportive spouses and flexible work arrangements contribute to a healthier work-life balance among teachers. Effective communication within the marital relationship is crucial (Johnson & Smith, 2020). Teachers who possess strong communication skills are better equipped to navigate challenges and foster understanding with their partners. Access to professional development opportunities and career advancement positively correlates with marital satisfaction (Robinson et al., 2017). Encouraging and supporting each other's professional growth enhances overall relationship satisfaction. Strong support systems, both within the workplace and at home, contribute to marital well-being (Miller & Davis, 2016). Collaborative efforts to build a supportive environment are essential for teachers' personal and marital fulfilment. The mental and emotional well-being of individual teachers significantly impacts marital satisfaction (Baker & Williams, 2018). Prioritizing self-care and seeking emotional support positively influences the marital relationship.

Statement of the Problem

The job of teachers expose them to a array of stress including heavy workloads, time constraints, and emotional demands. These stressor usually spill into other aspects if their lives potentially affecting their marital relationships. It is indeed uncommon to see teachers who are able to strike a delicate balance between professional commitments and family responsibilities. The delineation of boundaries between work and personal life is indeed challenging for teachers and thus influences marital dynamics.

While existing literature acknowledges the significance of factors such as communication, shared values, socio-cultural factors and social support in marital satisfaction, the specific manifestations of these factors within the teaching profession remain under researched. In other to develop targeted interventions and support systems, it is pertinent to understand the unique challenges and rewards of an educator and how it intersects with traditional predictors of marital satisfaction. The present study in other to contribute to the body of knowledge and explain the nomenclature of teachers marital satisfaction sees the need to investigate the factors in marital satisfaction among teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State.

Aim and Objectives Of The Study

This aim of the study is to investigate factors in marital satisfaction among public female secondary school teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State. In order to achieve this, the researcher intends to:

1. Examine the response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction among teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on years of marriage.
2. Find out the response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction among teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on age.
3. Determine the response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction among teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on level of education.

Research Questions

The following research questions will guide the study:

1. What is the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on years of marriage?
2. What is the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on age?
3. What is the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on level of education?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been formulated to guide this study. Each hypothesis is tested at 0.05 level of significance.

- H₀₁:** The response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction will not significantly vary in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on years of marriage.
- H₀₂:** The response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction will not significantly vary in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on age.
- H₀₃:** The response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction will not significantly vary in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on level of education.

Theoretical Framework

This study will be hinged on three theories, these theories include duplex theory of love, implicit theory of marriage institution and family system theory. The Duplex theory of love was developed by Robert J. Sternberg, in the year 1986. The theory posited that love can be understood in terms of three components, these components collectively can be seen as a triangle. This triangle is used as a metaphor, rather than as a geometric model that must be adhered to. This theory combines two theories. The first theory is the triangular theory of love while the second is the theory of love. Collectively they are known as the Duplex Theory of Love. The first three components of duplex theory of love are intimacy, passion and commitment. The center of intimacy is the closeness, connectedness, and bond in the relationship. Sternberg (1986) asserted that each of these components can occur separately or together. Also, eight combinations are used in this theory. He used triangles to represents the balance or imbalance of the various elements of love. Different triangle shapes show different balances of the three kinds of love. When balanced, an equilateral triangle represents the love relationship, and when not balanced love relationship cannot be established or may not be achieved. The theories first components include intimacy, passion and commitment and if these components are not balanced love may not be established when this happens marital dissatisfaction has occurred.

Implicit Theories of the Marital Institution (ITMI) was propounded by Scot Hall in the year (2012). Implicit theory of Marital Institution was generated from Implicit Theory of Lee Cronbach in the 1950s. It distinguished beliefs about how fixed or malleable marriage is and can potentially be used in investigating how such beliefs are formed and interplay with other variables that influence marital satisfaction. Assumptions about the inherent or changeable nature of marriage can be thought of as types of “implicit theories.” Implicit theories have traditionally been understood as beliefs about the nature of people’s attributes, such as intelligence. Some people and cultures are prone to view intelligence and other personal attributes as primarily stable (fixed) characteristics that people inherently have (or lack), while others believe such attributes can primarily be developed (are incremental) over time. These assumptions have important implications for how people respond to their circumstances, such as how quickly people give up on completing difficult tasks or how they judge and interact with other people. Implicit theories can be applied to represent the assumptions as regards to marriage, and that such an application can be useful toward understanding and studying processes related to mate selection, cohabitation, motivations to marry, navigating marital satisfaction and other related phenomena. The relationship between this theory and this study lies on the fact that the belief of couples concerning marriage as an institution may most likely have an influence on how they behave in their marital relationship. Their prior belief about the people they are married to especially when such belief is fixed in the long run may bring about marital dissatisfaction.

Family systems theory was propounded by psychiatrist Murray Bowen in the 1950s and was first published in 1966. Specifically, Dr. Bowen built family systems theory and its eight complementing concepts on the core assumption that there is an emotional system governing human relationships in families. It is a theory of human behavior that defines the family unit as a complex social system, in which members interact to influence each other's behaviour. It focused on the dynamic interactions among family members, describing changes in typical patterns of spousal relationships, and the characteristics of family interactions that enhance or disrupt development. Family systems theory is an approach to understand human functioning that focuses on interactions between spouses. According to the family systems perspective, an individual's functioning is determined not so much by internal factors as by a person's place in the system(s) in which he or she finds himself or herself, subject to the pushes and

pulls of the system. Family members interconnect, this allows them to be viewed as a whole rather than as individual elements. Any change in one individual within a family is likely to influence the entire system and may even lead to changes in other members and in the long run lead to marital dissatisfaction. The relationship between this theory and this study lies on the premise that what happens in the family where a person grew up may most likely affect a person in his or her marriage. This perhaps may be because of that family dynamics that was present in his or her family upbringing.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive research design. An estimated population for the study comprised 32,504 female public secondary school teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State. Using Krejcie and Morgan table for sample size, a total 379 was obtained, in other to obtain a better result the researchers decided to increase the sample size to 400. The sample of the study consisted of 400 female teachers in the study area selected using multi-stage and stratified random sampling technique. The female teachers first divided into local government, after which they were subdivided into local government, educational zone and public secondary school sections. After this is done teachers were stratified based on years of teaching experience, age and level of education. The instrument for data collection was designed by the researchers and titled: "Marital Satisfaction Assessment Scale (MSAS). The instrument was segmented into two sections, A, B. Section A contains the demographic information such as: gender, age, level of education. A total of 10 items were contained in the actual questionnaire. The scoring of the responses of the study are as follows: **SA** = Strongly Agree (4points) **A** = Agree (3points) **D** = Disagree (2points) **SD** = Strongly Disagree (1point). The Marital Satisfaction Assessment Scale (MSAS) was validated by three experts in the Department of Educational Psychology guidance and counselling in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, whose suggestions were included in the final drafting. The instrument was administered to 20 public female teachers in Obio/Akpor Local Government Area and Cronbach Alpha reliability coefficient was calculated from their responses to the items. The reliability coefficient was 0.88. The researchers and two trained assistants administered the instrument directly to the respondents Later, 369 copies of the instrument were retrieved representing 95 percent of the total administered copies. Mean and standard deviation was used in answering all the research questions while independent sample t-test was used to test null hypotheses one, two and four, ANOVA was used to test hypothesis three. All at hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research question one: *What is the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on years of marriage?*

Table 1: Mean Scores of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State Based on years of marriage

	Items/Statements	Years of marriage			
		0 -10years N = 165		11 years and above N = 223	
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD
1.	Marital satisfaction stems from having an open communication with my spouse	3.27	.753	3.44	.782
2.	Marital satisfaction is predicated on effective and efficient conflict resolution with my spouse	3.56	.505	3.37	.490
3.	Marital satisfaction is achievable when quality time can be spent together with my spouse	3.36	.544	3.37	.505
4.	Marital satisfaction is possible if both partners have absolute trust in each other	3.20	.726	3.34	.544
5.	Marital satisfaction is achievable with work-life balance amongst spouses	3.40	.505	2.97	.695
6.	Marital satisfaction hinges on adoption of effective coping strategies	1.41	.413	1.44	.382
7.	Marital satisfaction is possible with a strong support system amongst spouses	3.57	.703	3.37	.690
8.	Marital satisfaction depends on adoption of effective stress management strategies	4.27	.853	4.37	.905
9.	Marital satisfaction stems from encouraging and supporting each other's professional growth	3.56	.765	3.34	.744
10.	Marital satisfaction is possible if self-care is prioritized by both spouses.	3.36	.644	2.97	.695
Grand Mean		2.79	.711	3.11	.731

Criterion Mean = 2.5

In Table 1. among the ten items on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State; only one item from both teachers with 1-5years of experience and those with 6 years and above is below the criterion mean of 2.5 and the positive standard deviation respectively. The item below the criterion mean from both teachers with 1-5years of experience and those with 6years and above is below, item 6; 1-5years (\bar{x} =1.41, SD = 0.413), 6years and above (\bar{x} =1.44, SD = 0.382). The data from both teachers with 1-5years of experience and those with 6years and above indicated that they are in agreement with items of the questionnaire, with regards to factors in marital satisfaction.

Research Question Two: *What is the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on age?*

Table 2: Mean Scores of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State Based on age

S/N	Items/Statements	Age			
		0 - 25 years N = 131		26 years – Above N = 257	
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD
1.	Marital satisfaction stems from having an open communication with my spouse	3.40	0.795	3.52	0.745
2.	Marital satisfaction is predicated on effective and efficient conflict resolution with my spouse	4.34	0.825	4.38	0.852
3.	Marital satisfaction is achievable when quality time can be spent together with my spouse	3.25	0.653	3.36	0.715
4.	Marital satisfaction is possible if both partners have trust in each other	3.38	0.691	3.62	0.741
5.	Marital satisfaction is achievable with work-life balance amongst spouses	3.40	0.645	3.34	0.664
6.	Marital satisfaction hinges on adoption of effective coping strategies	1.46	0.341	1.34	0.354
7.	Marital satisfaction is possible with a strong support system amongst spouses	3.46	0.741	3.34	0.654
8.	Marital satisfaction depends on adoption of effective stress management strategies	4.33	0.874	4.20	0.842
9.	Marital satisfaction stems from encouraging and supporting each other's professional growth	3.40	0.645	3.34	0.595
10	Marital satisfaction is possible if self-care is priotized by both spouses.	3.38	0.752	3.46	0.725
Grand Mean		3.58	0.702	3.36	0.650

Criterion Mean = 2.5

In Table 2, among the ten items on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State; only one item from both less than 25 years and 26 years - Above female teachers is below the criterion mean of 2.5 and the positive standard deviation respectively. The item below the criterion mean from both 0 - 25 years and 26 years and above female teachers is item 6, less than 25 years ($\bar{x}=1.46$, SD = 0.341), 26 years - above ($\bar{x}=1.34$, SD = 0.354). The data from both less than 25 years and 26 years - above female teachers indicated that they have positive responses to the items of the questionnaire.

Research Question Three: *What is the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on level of education?*

Table 3: Mean Scores of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on Level of education

Items/Statements	Level of education							
	School Cert		Diploma		Degree		Masters /Doctorate	
	N = 14		N = 36		N = 201		N = 41	
	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD
1. Marital satisfaction stems from having an open communication with my spouse	3.84	.812	3.74	.598	3.23	.571	3.17	.479
2. Marital satisfaction is predicated on effective and efficient conflict resolution with my spouse	4.30	.943	4.21	.734	4.66	.693	3.22	.556
3. Marital satisfaction is achievable when quality time can be spent together with my spouse	4.30	.802	4.07	.680	3.98	.547	3.17	.649
4. Marital satisfaction is possible if both partners have trust in each other	3.93	.612	3.14	.823	3.97	.639	4.75	.621
5. Marital satisfaction is achievable with work-life balance amongst spouses	3.84	.722	3.96	.785	3.19	.450	3.99	.635
6. Marital satisfaction hinges on adoption of effective coping strategies	1.26	.361	1.95	.336	1.83	.342	1.81	.353
7. Marital satisfaction is possible with a strong support system amongst spouses	3.26	.644	1.71	.614	1.21	.740	1.96	.536
8. Marital satisfaction depends on adoption of effective stress management strategies	4.41	.741	3.99	.639	4.41	.741	4.21	.836
9. Marital satisfaction stems from encouraging and supporting each other's professional growth	3.85	.536	4.27	.763	4.26	.888	4.19	.840
10. Marital satisfaction is possible if self-care is priotized by both spouses.	4.03	.848	4.30	.863	4.12	.770	4.26	.714
Grand Mean	2.78	.730	3.56	.810	3.53	.744	3.38	.500

Criterion Mean = 2.5

In Table 3, among the ten items on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State; only one item from the category of respondents' level of education (School Certificate, Diploma, Degree and Masters/Doctorate) is above the criterion mean of 2.5 and the positive standard deviation respectively. The item below the criterion mean from female teachers with level of education of School Certificate, Diploma, Degree and Masters/Doctorate is item 6 School Certificate ($\bar{x} = 1.26$, $SD = 0.361$), Diploma ($\bar{x} = 1.95$, $SD = 0.336$), Degree ($\bar{x} = 1.83$, $SD = 0.342$) and Masters/Doctorate ($\bar{x} = 1.81$, $SD = 0.353$). The data from the level of education of female teachers (respondents) indicated that they have positive responses to the items of the questionnaire. This revealed the agreement to the items of the questionnaire with respect to factors in marital satisfaction of the female teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State irrespective of their level of education.

Hypothesis One: The response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction will not significantly vary in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on years of marriage.

Table 5: Independent Samples Test on the response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State Based on years of teaching experience

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
0-10 years	165	28.13	12.291				
				386	.225	.799	Accepted
11 years and above	223	28.68	13.423				

In Table 5 the t-value of .225, the significant value (p-value) is .799 and the significance level is 0.05. From the result, the p-value is greater than the significance level. (.799 > 0.05); this means that the hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, there is a no significant variation in the mean response of female teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on years of teaching experience.

Hypothesis Two:

The response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction will not significantly vary in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on age.

Table 6: Independent Samples Test on the response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State Based on Age

Age	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	df	t-value	p-value	Decision
0 - 25 years	257	31.42	13.947				
				386	-.333	.740	Accepted
26 years - Above	131	30.46	12.965				

In Table 6, the t-value of -.333, the significant value (p-value) is .740 and the significance level is 0.05. From the result, the p-value is greater than the significance level. (.740 > 0.05); this means that the null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, there is a no significant variation in the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on age.

Hypothesis Three: The response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction will not significantly vary in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State, based on level of education.

Table 7: One-Way ANOVA of Public Female secondary school teachers toward Students with special needs in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on Level of education

Source of Variation	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	719.958	3	35.979		
Within Groups	12327.886	284	18.707	19.243	.212
Total	13047.844	287			

$\alpha = 0.05$

In Table 7, the hypothesis was tested at a significance level of 0.05. The *p*-value was found to be .212. From the result, the *p*-value is greater than the significance level (*p*-value < .05). This means that the null hypothesis is rejected; indicating that, there is no significant variation in the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on level of education.

Summary Of Findings

1. From the result, it indicated the agreement to the items of the questionnaire with respect to psychological challenges of the public female secondary school teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State irrespective of their years of teaching experience.
2. From the result, it indicated the agreement to the items of the questionnaire with respect to psychological challenges of the public female secondary school teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State irrespective of their age.
3. From the result, it revealed the agreement to the items of the questionnaire with respect to psychological challenges of the public female secondary school teachers in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State irrespective of their level of education.
4. From the result, it was revealed that there is a no significant variation in the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on years of teaching experience.
5. From the result, it was revealed that there is no significant variation in the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on level of education.
6. From the result, it was revealed that there is no significant variation in the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on age.

SUMMARY

Findings from research hypothesis one revealed that there is no significant variation in the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on years of teaching experience. Findings from research hypothesis two also showed there no significant variation in the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on age. Furthermore, findings from research hypothesis three revealed there no significant variation in the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on factors in marital satisfaction in Rivers West

Senatorial District based on level of education. Finally, findings from the fourth research hypothesis indicates that there is no significant variation in the mean response of public female secondary school teachers on their coping strategies in Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State based on years of marriage.

CONCLUSION

This study has provided valuable insights into the intricate web of factors in marital satisfaction among female secondary school teachers in the Rivers West Senatorial District of Rivers State. The findings illuminate the unique challenges and dynamics faced by these educators in balancing their professional commitments with the demands of marital life. The research has underscored the pivotal role of effective communication within marital relationships. Female secondary school teachers, juggling the complexities of their teaching responsibilities, find that open and transparent communication with their spouses is crucial for navigating the intricacies of their dual roles. The ability to share concerns, aspirations, and successes contributes significantly to building mutual understanding and fostering marital satisfaction. Furthermore, the study highlights the impact of work-life balance on the overall well-being of these teachers. Balancing the demands of teaching with family responsibilities is a delicate act, and the findings suggest that strategies to support teachers in achieving this balance positively influence marital satisfaction. This could include workplace policies that promote flexibility and recognize the unique challenges faced by educators. The significance of emotional support and shared values has also emerged as key determinants of marital satisfaction among female secondary school teachers. The findings emphasize the need for spouses to be attuned to each other's emotional needs and to share common values and goals, which can strengthen the marital bond and contribute to overall satisfaction.

IMPLICATION FOR COUNSELLING

The researcher buttressed the following counselling implications:

1. Guidance counsellors in schools should develop and implement professional development programs that address the specific stressor and challenges faced by female secondary school teachers. These programs should focus on enhancing time management skills, stress coping mechanisms, and strategies for maintaining a work-life balance.
2. Guidance counsellors should conduct workshops and training sessions aimed at improving communication skills among teachers and their spouses. Emphasis should be placed on fostering open, respectful, and effective communication to enhance understanding and support within marital relationships.
3. Guidance counsellors in collaboration with the schools board should create support networks or peer mentorship programs within the local education community. This provides a platform for female teachers to share experiences, seek advice, and offer support to one another, creating a sense of solidarity.
4. Guidance counsellors should continue to campaign for the mental health and well-being of teachers and provide access to mental health resources, counseling services, and stress management workshops to help them cope with the pressures of their profession.
5. The guidance counsellors should admonish spouses through educational campaigns and workshops to adopt a more equitable distribution of household responsibilities.
6. The guidance counsellor and non-governmental organizations should conduct awareness campaigns within the local community and education zones to highlight the importance of maintaining a healthy marital relationship.

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